

Role and Need of Modern Public Relation Practices in Policing: Mapping a Pathway

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Keywords

Policing, Public Police Interface, Governance, Public Relation Practices.

Abstract

In a democratic society like India where various stakeholders viz. good governance, civil society, non-government institutions, accountability, need for internal security through effective policing, role of media, etc have come into the significant stream (Sharma & Marwah¹). The need of effective public police interface is considered principal solution in establishing mutual coherence in making of a smooth society. The study finds that practice of public police interface is considered panacea but there are gaps that exist between the successful public and police connects. On basis of analyzing literature available on public police interface, we have deduced that police have failed to connect successfully with the different strata of society. The present study analyzes and evaluates the various dimensions of public police interface, its significance, challenges and brings forth the prospects of public relation tools and practices in ushering effective public police interface.

Introduction

IN a developing nation like India, government plays an important role in managing public affairs and to keep the growth of country on track. Modern day government is not only the provider of services but also the agent of social change. Government is not a standalone term these days but its nomenclature is replaced by a modern term

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'Governance'. Governance is a different term from government i.e. former is a qualitative concept whereas latter one is a physical entity². Generally governance refers to the decision making and implementation processes in the administration of a country, state or organization. Governance refers to the 'governability' of a polity or, in other words, the capacity of a political system to govern efficiently and to provide necessary political conditions for socio economic development³. So, governance is government in action or government carrying out its functions to manage public affairs. Governance being a neutral term focuses only on functioning of government.

With the advent of liberalization, globalization and privatization reforms in India in 1991 many international agencies recognize absence of effective governance as a serious barrier to overall development. This was the time when a new modified term of governance emerged i.e. 'Good Governance'. Good governance is a term that connotes value assumptions. Authors define good governance as unambiguously identifying the basic values of society and pursuing these⁴. It is accompanied by certain values which installs positive virtues of administration and elimination of vices of dysfunctions. Good governance is attached with effective and efficient public administration in a democratic set up. Pai Panandiker sees good governance as it pertains to a nation which handles its people to lead peaceful, orderly, reasonable, prosperous, participatory lives⁵. It refers to the adoption of new values of government to establish greater efficiency, legitimacy and credibility of the system.

Good governance is a wider term which covers into its ambit various elements like rule of law, accountability, decentralization, honesty and independence of judiciary, human rights, people's participation, equality and absence of discrimination. So, good governance is an uphill task in which various stakeholders play their respective roles.

Government being the dominant actor plays an important role in formulating and implementing public policies which aim at achieving objectives of good governance. Government has multiple functions and multifarious agencies which perform their respective functions. As Weber remarks that state is a multifaceted entity⁶.

In modern day governance, law and order is an important function for any government, but at the same time it poses a big challenge also. Law and order function is associated with police organization

of government. Effective law and order demands the application of rule of law. Rule of law is one of the fundamental characteristics of good governance. It entails certain principles which lay the foundation for working of every police organization; some of these principles are absence of arbitrary power, equality before law and primacy of rights of individuals. So, police being protector of citizen's life should maintain the principles of rule of law. Undoubtedly effective police reforms can certainly help to strengthen confidence in the rule of law⁷.

Rationale of Public-Police Interface

In a democratic polity maintenance of law and order is heart of governance. Increasing crime rates in any society reflects its negative image. Accordingly, it becomes the duty of police to curb evil practices in society and set an example of effective law and order. But in a country like India, police has a poor image in public. It is viewed as an oppressive tool in the hands of political masters. Whatever policies are formulated by government regarding law and order are implemented by police as line agencies. The police are the edge, the most visible and, according to many citizens, the most approachable of these criminal justices practioners⁸. The activities performed by police directly affects the behaviour of public. The general trend of opinion is that the public hates police and that police act harshly and oppressively towards the public. This portrays negative image of police in minds of the citizens. In this backdrop, it is imperative to have an effective and strong public police interface which will help to improve the relation between the two. In a democracy aiming at welfare state, it is essential that members of this vital service of police should cultivate harmonious relations with the public and should help the people in distress and trouble⁹.

Another dimension of public police interface is community policing. Community policing draws its genesis from 'communitarianism' approach given by Amitai Etzioni¹⁰. In this approach aim is to make community participate in local level governance. They join hands with government agencies to solve local level problems and to achieve objectives of grass root governance. On the same lines community policing aims at improving the relationship between the service provider i.e. police and its beneficiaries i.e. public. A good example would be that of a Neighbourhood Watch Scheme designed to involve the community and police in policing their surroundings¹¹.

Literature Review

Several academicians and practitioners have advocated and facilitated the public police interface and community policing. Police is recognised as coercive arm of government to control crime, but there are frequent debates like extending human relations training of officers, developing programme to educate the public about the functioning of police and creating community relation units within departments, all these practices aim at changing role of police in society¹². At the same time the police officer should be philosopher, guide and friend or that the police officer should be a helper. Line officers should be concerned with the preservation of peace, protection of life and property, enforcement of laws and detection of law breakers¹³.

Theoretically it is easy to talk about friendly public police interface or involvement of public in policing, but some examinations are being carried out regarding nature of public police support in normal and some extra ordinary situations like in strikes, riots and such other instances of social disorder, natural calamities and communal tensions. It was deduced that in these situations complete dependence is on police machinery¹⁴. No doubt primary role of police is prevention of crime and maintenance of law and order, but this role should be played with deference to the satisfaction of the people as police is not supposed to rule but to serve¹⁵. Even in the ancient times police administration in the villages was collective responsibility of every resident in order to help police in uniform patrolling, crime investigation and prevention of crime. Such administration was based on principle of local responsibility and mutual cooperation¹⁶. Such mutual cooperation and collective responsibility is missing in present scenario due to lack of effective public police relations practices. Image of police is tarnished in the minds of public. There is a need to lay stress on police public relations which aims at developing favourable attitude of public towards police¹⁷. Such absence of public relation with police can be drawn from colonial past where police aimed at serving less. Since independence situation has not improved due to lack of public participation. Therefore public police interface has failed to ripe expected results¹⁸. Effective and strong public police interface can be devised by evaluating citizen's attitude towards policing. In this backdrop, a study was conducted in which special attention was given to role of media and direct contact with service providers¹⁹. With the passage of time expectations of public are changing regarding police.

In order to meet these complex expectations, community Policing practices would be an effective tool. It can help to change the attitude of citizens regarding police²⁰. It is vivid that community policing is an imperative tool, but it cannot be implemented until and unless it is defined conceptually. A study was carried out, in which complex interactions in community policing, role conflicts, impact of media and evolution of police community relation was mapped²¹. Lastly community policing requires a benchmark leadership. Leaders and youngsters always play a positive role in shaping minds of society. So strategies should be devised to figure out young local youngsters and to keep them away from drug abuse and negative evils. Such strategies can be helpful in mobilizing local talent and to get information regarding local criminal activities²².

Need of Effective Public Police Interface

The public police interface is an organizational philosophy which stands on effective communication and interaction with various strata of society. Police organization is a not a standalone entity, it is the form of integral part of society. Society can be termed as system in which various interdependent parts play their respective roles and give shape to a major role played by a system. In this backdrop we can deduce that society is a system in which public and police are interdependent parts which performs their respective roles. In modern day governance connectivity of police with public is pivotal. The following points depict the importance of public police interface in making a balanced society:

- **Meeting the Needs of Society:** The primary function of police is maintenance of law and order. But with the change of time, functions of police have also become complex and diverse. In order to cater to the needs of citizens, it becomes important to figure out and meet the expectations. Such needs must be understood by the police then it can direct its efforts towards the expected performance and efficient policing.
- **Positive Image Building:** Generally police has a poor public image. It is viewed as an oppressive force in society. Malfunctioning and corruption in policing have portrayed negative image of police amongst citizens. In order to overcome this daunting situation, it is imperative that police should devise some plans through which its image can be improved. Rigorous promotions, campaigns

and highlighting positive works can contribute to the positive outcomes.

- **Effective Feedback Mechanisms:** Feedback is a crucial tool through which connectivity can be built between two ends. It will also lessen the gap between public and police which will lead to better understanding and winning trust amongst the public. In order to have strong public police interface it is important that police should ask people for feedback of their performance. For ensuring this, periodic surveys and interviews must be conducted as collected information will help police to analyze its performance and also to set the further higher standards for delivering services to the citizens.
- **Participation in Police Governance:** In a democratic setup, it is important for police organization to educate people regarding the participative governance. Police public participation in crime prevention is a new dimension in police governance. Such collaboration will help both the parties in understanding each other and also to cooperate in crisis situation. As people will participate in policing, they will get a chance to learn safety techniques and also how to react in crisis situations.

Challenges of Effective Public Police Interface

Public police interface aims at philosophy, managerial style and organizational plan that promote better public police partnership and more proactive problem solving approach towards the community. It helps in providing solution to wide range of problems and issues involving crime control, crime prevention and the fear of crime. Public police interface is based on collaboration between police and citizens in an amiable and cooperative spirit.

It is not that easy to achieve effective collaboration of public police interface in practice. There are various hurdles which pose danger in the way. The image of police is harsh amongst the society. People find police oppressive and often hesitate to have any form of communication with them. The behaviour of police is rude and practices like maltreatment and corruption are often highlighted in media. Another grave concern is lack of soft skills and human relations approach in policing which arouse fear in society defeating the very purpose of public police interface. Besides this, police hesitate or ignore to keep in touch with public. These omissions and commissions

betray the poor training practices. Police is not trained in respect of public relation approach which is a dominant feature of modern day police governance. Above all there is absence of the marketisation of police service. Here marketing emphasizes a management process which identifies and satisfy citizens requirement efficiently.

In order to overcome all these issues, the following section projects the implementation of modern day public relation tools and practices to usher effective public police interface. With the advent of these tools and managerial practices police personnel are supposed to be public managers who along with curbing crime also promote themselves as efficient public servants, tackling the crisis situations without breaching the ethical conduct and public good.

Role of Public Relations in effective Public Police Interface

Improving police department's image in the community takes more than just a concern or wishful thinking. The police department must establish an effective partnership with the community as a whole, the foundation of which is mutual trust and understanding. Police organizations must realize that they have the ability to alter their own image within the community.

Here the role of modern day public relation practices becomes important in making police reach at the doorsteps of people. Generally, public relation practices are considered as collection of communication techniques used by individuals or organizations to convey the public or media about the merits of an organization, programme or a policy. The matter of maintaining good relations with the public involves much more than trying to please an indistinguishable mass of people²³. It involves trying to satisfy all those elements of divergent likes and dislikes in the society²⁴. It is in this backdrop that the role of public relations in modern day public police interface is eminent. Effective public relation practices are the collection of creative techniques used for image building, enhancing internal and as well external coordination, handling and yielding media benefits for dissemination of knowledge²⁵. All these techniques play a significant role as these tools can change the image of police which in turn reflects the degree of public confidence and respect for policing. So, here role of modern day public relation practices becomes important to shun the negative image of police from minds of people through effective public relation practices. Police can build stronger connectivity with public by

ushering in the community policing and improving the public police interface. The following public relation practices depict importance in different dimensions which are as follows:

- Through public relations practices like feed-back, surveys, harnessing coordinated campaigns, focussed group discussions police can highlight its vision and mission amongst citizen's thereby building trust. Such practices will bridge the gap and bring community more closer to the police.
- Holding meetings with resident welfare associations and briefing them about emerging trends of crimes will provide a platform to public to participate in public governance. Such meeting will yield suggestions for police to strengthen the policing gaps.
- Distributing printed material like brochures, verification forms and helpline numbers will raise the inquisitiveness of citizens to participate in community policing projects. There is need to have a complete Public relation unit in police department which must research the trends of crime and thereby designing the nature of activities. All the activities of community policing must be well advertised in various modes e.g. public service advertisements, flex advertisements, moving advertisements on public transport .These tools of persuasive communication will enhance the mutual understanding.
- With the advent of public relation and management practices, marketing the police would appear a practical exercise to undertake, and putting the citizen at the centre of police planning and activities may provide answers to many problems the police facing today. Marketing can be conducted through two processes²⁶:
 - a) **Internal marketing:** In order to build strong public police relations, there is need to inculcate citizen centric policing among policemen. It can be done through internal marketing which aims at communicating with policemen at all the levels of police hierarchy and involving them in new initiatives and strategies. It helps to create spirit de corps and sense of team work among policemen. The following table describe the desired organizational and structural transformation which is needed for implementing the citizen centric policing.

Organizational and structural transformation aims to achieve desired goals. Changes in structure involve organizational and policy matter designing in recruitment, training, rewards, promotion and the establishment of specialized police units. As far structure is concerned, effective participative policing involves the shift as described in table below:

Traditional Policing	Citizen Centric Policing
a centralized structure	a decentralised structure (the aim is to bring the police closer to the community)
excessive specialization	a balance between versatility and specialization
standardization and uniformity	flexibility and diversity
an autocratic “command and control” style of management	a participative and consultative style of management
operational management of status quo	strategic leadership of change
a focus on short term strategies	a focus on the long term impact of strategies
a narrow definition of the duties of a patrol officer - their role is limited to attending to complaints and they must always act according to the “book”	an extension of the duties of the patrol officer - the patrol officer becomes a generalist responsible for attending complaints, solving problems, activating the community, preventing crime, and undertaking preliminary crime investigations. The discretionary powers of the patrol officer are recognized and developed.
narrow training emphasis on fitness, self-defense and knowledge of the law	a broader training focus which, in addition to fitness, self-defense and knowledge of the law, include knowledge of crime prevention, conflict resolution, problem-solving, and community participation
Head Office as a source of orders, rules and regulations	Head Office as a source of support, direction, norms and values
the measurement of performance based on “quantitative” criteria such as the number of arrests	the measurement of performance based on “qualitative” criteria such as the achievement of community goals or the solution of problems
heavy dependence on rules and regulations	a value driven approach based on the policing vision

Source: Manual on Community Policing Policy, Framework and Guidelines (South Africa), Retrieved from www.thecpf.co.za/request.php

Such transformation is not possible overnight, role of effective public relation practices play a worthy role in shaping the organizational culture which can be carried out by continuous effective leadership and sensitization of police personnel at every level.

It can be depicted from the table that the traditional role of police no longer exists. These days more emphasis is on citizen centric policing in which citizen is considered sovereign. Modern policing requires decentralized structure which can shatter the barriers of old centralized policing with more scope of police participation. Moreover, role and duties of police has also undergone a change, increasing ambit of police functioning with more versatility and specialisation. More emphasis is given on educating police personnel about importance of fitness, crime prevention, knowledge of law and community participation. Performance of police has always been under scanner of citizens, so modern policing aims at quality rather quantity in achieving the goals of community. Police ultimately deals with public who have certain values which sometimes cannot be in consonance with rigid rules and regulations devised to control citizens. Here focus should be on a value driven approach in which citizen should be at centre. This transformation calls for strong public relation practices which can help in knitting strong public police interface. Some of these techniques can be advertising of the police work. The advertising is generally a mass communication technique through which a target group is sent a message. In policing, advertising can play an effective role in connecting with public. Through advertising police can create awareness regarding effective police functioning, new strategies for maintenance of law and order and in receiving feedback from citizens which will help police to understand the public perception. Secondly, a public relations department can be established in all police departments which will be involved in conducting rigorous public relation practices and thereby connecting police with community. For this, police personnel should be given a formal training in which they can be taught soft skills as how to connect with people. Such practices will help to provide a pragmatic shape to this sound idea of community policing.

- b) **Interactive marketing:** Interactive marketing aims at forming a communication channel through which police can interact with public. A police officer should see public as a client with aim to provide service. Such interactive marketing will help police to create awareness among public regarding new police activities and

plans devised for public care. In return, public can also provide feedback regarding service delivery performance of police. It aims at highlighting good work of police, and change public perception about the police. But here attitude and behaviour of each police officer is crucial. So, police personnel should be given training regarding interaction skills and attitude.

Apart from aforementioned techniques, role of media is also imperative in strengthening the public police relations. Media is an important democratic resource and plays a pivotal role in developing the understanding between police and public. They have, therefore, a strong potential to serve as a positive force towards improving the system of public police relations. Media helps to generate awareness and disseminate information among public regarding police activities. It also plays a crucial role in the development of citizens to be active in police governance²⁷. Generally media highlights malpractices in police governance. So role of media should be to portray positive image of police in society and appreciate the activities conducted by police for public safety. The role of effective spokesperson is of utmost importance for repairing the tarnished image through rebuttal, rejoinders and media conferences.

Conclusion

Presently, police administration has undergone a change in comparison with traditional one. Now police is much more accountable and responsible to public for their actions. Police functions have increased in consonance with public awareness, so having good relations with public is the need of hour. On basis of above discussion we can deduce that upgrading modern public relation practices have become a prospective area of concern for police to knit strong public police interface and connect the values of police and public.

Endnotes

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